

Weak geometric optical knot in vacuum (2+1)-dimensional space-time

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We propose the existence of a topological object, a weak geometric optical knot, in the framework of an Abelian Chern-Simons action in vacuum (2+1)-dimensional space-time. This idea is based on the treatment of geometrical optics as a local $U(1)$ gauge theory and the field strength tensor could consist of a set of subset fields that satisfies the non-trivial Hopf maps, resulting in topological structures. We derive the corresponding field equations and propose an ansatz solution that supports the formation of such knots under weak-field conditions.

Keywords: *geometrical optics, Abelian Chern-Simons action, weak field, vacuum, Minkowski (2+1)-dimensional space-time, knot.*

I. INTRODUCTION

It has been widely believed that topological objects can not exist in linear theories. Topological theories are inherently non-linear¹. How, then, could a topological object, a weak geometric optical knot, exist in the linear theory, such as an Abelian Chern-Simons theory?

The existence of a topological object, a knot, in Maxwell's theory, has been well known¹⁻⁴. In Maxwell's theory, the electromagnetic fields (the set of the solutions of Maxwell equations) in vacuum could consist of a set of subset fields, complex scalar fields, with the topological structure¹⁻³. It means that the scalar fields have a non-trivial topology. What we mean by vacuum here is a space without charge and current⁵. This set of subset fields satisfies the non-trivial Hopf maps. It means that the non-trivial Hopf maps could describe the properties of a set of subset fields¹⁻³. Throughout this article, we will work with the real classical scalar field. This real scalar field can be interpreted in the same way as the real scalar potential.

A set of subset fields is locally equal to the Abelian field strength tensor, i.e. the Abelian field strength tensor can be obtained by patching together a set of subset fields (except in a zero-measure set) but globally different. The difference is global, instead of local, since a set of subset fields obeys the topological quantum condition, but the Abelian field strength tensor does not. The Abelian field strength tensor satisfies the linear field theory, but a set of subset fields satisfies the non-linear field theory. Both, the Abelian field strength tensor and a set of subset fields, satisfy the linear field theory in the case of a weak-field limit where the non-linear field theory is reduced to the linear field theory¹⁻³.

In this article, we propose that a weak geometric optical knot exists in vacuum (2+1)-dimensional space-time. What we mean by the weak geometric optical knot is a geometric optical knot of weak-field limit where the amplitude is very small and has a constant value in a

vacuum. A non-zero amplitude ensures that the scalar field remains smooth and well-defined throughout space-time. The phase remains mathematically well-defined in this limit. Because, if the amplitude is zero then the scalar field is also zero. It implies that the phase becomes physically meaningless or undetermined since any phase choice gives the same trivial result. The reason is true there exists an electromagnetic knot in Maxwell's theory¹⁻⁴ and the geometrical optics can be treated as an Abelian $U(1)$ local gauge theory^{6,7} such as Maxwell's theory (the eikonal equation in geometrical optics can be derived from Maxwell equations⁸⁻¹⁰). To the best of our knowledge^{1-4,11-16}, the formulation of the weak geometric optical knot has not been done yet.

This article is organized as follows. In Section II, we discuss in brief our treatment of geometrical optics as $U(1)$ gauge theory in vacuum (2+1)-dimensional space-time. In Section III, the relation between phase, eikonal, and refractive index is described. In Section IV, the wave point of view is used to describe the scalar and gauge potentials. The Clebsch scalar variables are used to write the gauge potential. In Section V, we discuss the non-trivial Hopf maps. In Section VI, the Hopf invariant and Hopf index relation is discussed in brief. In Section VII, we show explicitly the Abelian Chern-Simons action. In Section VIII, we formulate the geometric optical knot related to topological current, the winding number. In Section IX, the field equations are derived and the ansatz for solutions are proposed. The discussion and conclusion are given in Section X.

II. GEOMETRICAL OPTICS AS $U(1)$ GAUGE THEORY

The treatment of geometrical optics as $U(1)$ local gauge theory implies that we have the concept of the gauge potential and the field strength tensor in geometrical optics such as in Maxwell's theory. The gauge po-

tential can be written as

$$A_\mu = a_\mu(\vec{r}, t) e^{iq(\vec{r}, t)} \quad (1)$$

where $a_\mu(\vec{r}, t)$ is an amplitude, a slowly varying function of space coordinates (the position vector, \vec{r}) and time, t ¹⁷, $q(\vec{r}, t)$ is a (real) phase¹⁸, i is an imaginary number, $\mu = 0, 1, 2$, represents the indices for Minkowski (2+1)-dimensional space-time. We represent vacuum as Minkowski (flat) space-time.

The related Abelian field strength tensor can be written as

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu A_\nu - \partial_\nu A_\mu \quad (2)$$

where ∂_μ represents the partial derivative with respect to the coordinate x^μ , i.e. $\partial_\mu = \partial/\partial x^\mu$, and it is often associated with the gradient operator in the context of field theory.

In $U(1)$ local gauge theory, the gauge potential and the amplitude are typically taken as real quantities, both are vectors. The gauge potential, such as the amplitude, can be interpreted as the oscillating variable¹⁹, the displacement from an equilibrium²⁰ (an equilibrium is a position at infinity where the gauge potential is assumed equal to zero). In that case, the phase (an angle) determines the instantaneous state of an oscillating gauge potential within the oscillating cycle, specifying whether it is at its maximum, minimum, or intermediate value.

III. PHASE, EIKONAL AND REFRACTIVE INDEX

To simplify the problem, our formulation of the weak geometric optical knot is only concerned with a steady monochromatic wave where the angular frequency remains constant. Here, "steady" means that the wave does not change over time except for a periodic oscillation, i.e. the only change happening over time is the regular, repeating oscillation of the wave, nothing else changes. In other words, the wave oscillates at a single, precise angular frequency, without any spread or uncertainty in its value. This corresponds to a perfectly monochromatic wave with a single spectral line (colour) in the optical spectrum.

The time dependence of the phase, q , is given by a term $-\omega t$ ¹⁷. We can write it as

$$\partial_t q = -\omega \quad (3)$$

where ω denotes an angular frequency. The negative sign (3) ensures the correct description of a right-moving wave in the standard wave equation formulation. It follows from the natural differentiation of the phase expression $q = kx - \omega t$, where k is the wave number, x is the spatial coordinate.

The relation between the phase and the eikonal, $\psi(\vec{r})$, can be written as¹⁷

$$\psi(\vec{r}) = \frac{c}{\omega} q(\vec{r}, t) + ct \quad (4)$$

where the eikonal is "a length" of line in space, a real²¹ scalar function of the position vector, and c is the speed of light in vacuum.

From eq.(4), the phase can be written as

$$q(\vec{r}, t) = \lambda \{\psi(\vec{r}) - ct\} \quad (5)$$

where $\lambda = \omega/c$ is a constant, and the eikonal can be related to the refractive index as written below¹⁷

$$\psi(\vec{r}) = \int_C n(\vec{r}) ds \quad (6)$$

where $n(\vec{r})$ is the refractive index, ds is an infinitesimal path length, and C denotes a path or curve along which the integration is performed. Physically, C could correspond to the path of a light ray traveling through space. The refractive index is the real scalar function of the position vector, the slowness at a point⁶. It is typically supplied as known input, given, and we seek the solution, the eikonal⁶.

By substituting eq.(6) into eq.(5), we obtain

$$q(\vec{r}, t) = \lambda \int_C n(\vec{r}) ds - \omega t \quad (7)$$

Eq.(7) is very interesting. The treatment of geometrical optics as gauge theory has a fundamental consequence that we might have the refractive index transformation which has a role similar to the gauge (phase) transformation.

IV. POTENTIAL, FIELD STRENGTH AND CLEBSCH VARIABLES

A scalar field or a scalar potential in geometrical optics can be written as

$$\phi(\vec{r}, t) = \rho(\vec{r}, t) e^{iq(\vec{r}, t)} \quad (8)$$

where $\rho(\vec{r}, t)$ is the scalar amplitude, $q(\vec{r}, t)$ is given in eq.(7). Eq.(9) is based on the assumption of the wave point of view of the field. The scalar field (9) could be interpreted as the disturbance where the physical disturbance is its real part²².

It is defined that

$$f(\vec{r}, t) = -1/\{2\pi(1 + \rho^2)\} \quad (9)$$

where $f(\vec{r}, t)$ denotes the function of amplitude. The phase, q , and the amplitude function, f , are called the Clebsch (scalar) variables³ or Gaussian potentials²³. These Clebsch variables are related to any divergenceless vector field¹, like the magnetic field, \vec{B} , where $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0$. The divergenceless property of any vector field means that there is no source to give rise to such a vector field. It has a consequence that $\vec{B} = \nabla \times \vec{A}$, where \vec{A} is the magnetic potential. The Clebsch variables are not uniquely defined (many different choices are possible for them)¹.

By using the Clebsch variables, eqs.(1), (2), could be written, respectively, as

$$A_\mu = f \partial_\mu q \quad (10)$$

$$F_{\mu\nu} = \partial_\mu(f \partial_\nu q) - \partial_\nu(f \partial_\mu q) \quad (11)$$

In a vacuum, the amplitude ρ is constant²⁴. In the case of the weak-field limit, ρ is very small, so that ρ^2 in eq.(9) can be ignored. It has a consequence that eq.(9) becomes

$$f = -1/2\pi \quad (12)$$

Because π is a constant, eq.(12) is valid in the case of the weak-field limit and a vacuum.

By substituting eq.(12) into eqs.(10), (11), we obtain

$$A_\mu = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \partial_\mu q \quad (13)$$

$$F_{\mu\nu} = -\frac{1}{2\pi} (\partial_\mu \partial_\nu q - \partial_\nu \partial_\mu q) \quad (14)$$

Eqs.(13), (14), are the equations of the gauge potential and the related field strength tensor in a vacuum and the weak-field limit.

V. HOPF MAPS

The property of a scalar potential can be interpreted by the non-trivial Hopf maps written below¹⁻³

$$\phi(\vec{r}) : S^3 \rightarrow S^2 \quad (15)$$

where S^3 and S^2 are three and two-dimensional spheres (space), respectively.

A set of subset fields consisting of a scalar potential has properties that, by definition, its value for a finite distance depends on the magnitude and direction of the position vector. But, for an infinite distance, it is well-defined² (it depends on the magnitude only). In other words, a scalar potential is isotropic for an infinite distance. We consider that the reduction of (one) dimensional space in the Hopf maps (16) could be interpreted as a consequence of the isotropic (well-defined) property of the scalar field for an infinite distance.

The Hopf maps (16) can be classified in homotopy classes, labeled by the value of the corresponding Hopf indexes, integer numbers, and the topological invariants^{1,2}. The other names of the topological invariants are the topological charge, the winding number (the degree of a continuous mapping)²⁵. The topological charge is metric tensor-independent. It could be interpreted as energy²⁶.

Scalar potential or scalar field in the non-trivial Hopf maps (16) are written as the time-independent scalar field. It differs from the time-dependent scalar field in Maxwell's theory, e.g. $\phi(\vec{r}, t)$, which relates to the magnetic field. This problem is solved by interpreting some of the quantities that appear in Hopf's theories as Cauchy's initial time values³.

VI. HOPF INVARIANT AND HOPF INDEX

The Hopf invariant, \mathcal{H} , in the integral form, can be written as^{12,27,28}

$$\mathcal{H} = \frac{1}{32\pi^2} \int_{S^3} \varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho} A_\mu F_{\nu\rho} d^3x \quad (16)$$

where $\varepsilon^{\mu\nu\rho}$ is the antisymmetric tensor of the Levi-Civita symbol. The integral is taken over the three-space, d^3x represents the volume element on the three-sphere.

The Hopf invariant relates to the Hopf index, h , as follows¹

$$\mathcal{H} = h \gamma^2 \quad (17)$$

where γ is the total strength of the field, that is the sum of the strengths of all the tubes formed by the integral lines of magnetic and electric fields¹.

It can be interpreted naturally that the Hopf invariant has a deep relationship with the Chern-Simons action in gauge theory and the self-helicity in magnetohydrodynamics¹². The Hopf invariant is just the winding number of Gauss mapping¹². Hopf invariant is an important topological invariant to describe the topological characteristics of the knot family^{12,16}. In a more precise expression, the Hopf invariant is the total sum of all the self-linking and all the linking numbers of the knot family^{12,16}. The self-linking and linking numbers by themselves have a topological structure.

VII. CHERN-SIMONS ACTION

The mathematical framework developed by Maxwell to formulate Faraday's theory of electromagnetism has subsequently been applied to pure mathematics, particularly in describing bundles over even-dimensional manifolds using characteristic classes. The study of bundles over odd-dimensional manifolds, incorporating secondary characteristic classes, was later introduced by Chern and Simons²⁹, leading to the development of Chern-Simons theory, a topological gauge theory in three-dimensional space-time³⁰. Topologically massive gauge theory is one of the first applications of the Chern-Simons action in physics²⁹.

The Abelian Chern-Simons action in three-dimensional space can be written as^{16,29}

$$S_{CS} = \frac{1}{8\pi} \int_M \varepsilon^{\alpha\beta\gamma} A_\alpha F_{\beta\gamma} d^3x \quad (18)$$

where M is the three-dimensional Euclidean space, and $\alpha, \beta, \gamma = 1, 2, 3$. The Chern-Simons action (18) is invariant under general coordinate transformations³¹. Notably, the Abelian Chern-Simons action (18) is mathematically equivalent to the Hopf invariant (16).

VIII. CHERN-SIMONS IN GEOMETRICAL OPTICS

The Abelian Chern-Simons action could be formulated in the geometrical optics, h_{go} , written as¹⁶

$$h_{\text{go}} = \frac{1}{8\pi} \int_M \varepsilon^{\alpha\mu\nu} A_\alpha F_{\mu\nu} d^{2+1}x \quad (19)$$

where $\varepsilon^{\alpha\mu\nu}$ is the Levi-Civita symbol, and $\alpha, \mu, \nu = 0, 1, 2$, M denotes (2+1)-dimensional Minkowski space-time.

The topological current can be defined^{14,16} as

$$J^\alpha = \frac{1}{8\pi} \varepsilon^{\alpha\mu\nu} F_{\mu\nu} \quad (20)$$

By substituting eq.(20) into (19), we obtain

$$h_{\text{go}} = \int_M A_\alpha J^\alpha d^{2+1}x \quad (21)$$

Eq.(21) could also be written as^{15,16}

$$h_{\text{go}} = \sum_{k=1}^N W_k \oint_{\gamma_k} A_\alpha dx^\alpha \quad (22)$$

where W_k is the winding number, an integer, $\gamma_k (k = 1, \dots, N)$ represents N Chern-Simons vortex lines of closed curves which form a family of N knotted closed curves.

IX. THE FIELD EQUATIONS AND SOLUTION

By substituting eq.(13) into (22), we have

$$h_{\text{go}} = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{k=1}^N W_k \oint_{\gamma_k} \partial_\alpha q dx^\alpha \quad (23)$$

The corresponding field equations can be derived by applying the variational principle to the action (23), we obtain

$$\delta h_{\text{go}} = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{k=1}^N W_k \delta \oint_{\gamma_k} \partial_\alpha q dx^\alpha = 0 \quad (24)$$

where δ denotes a small variation, the infinitesimal changes or perturbations.

By assuming that δ and the partial derivative is commute, we can write eq.(24) as

$$\delta h_{\text{go}} = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{k=1}^N W_k \oint_{\gamma_k} \partial_\alpha (\delta q) dx^\alpha = 0 \quad (25)$$

The Stokes' theorem is

$$\oint_{\gamma_k} \partial_\alpha (\delta q) dx^\alpha = \int_{V_k} \partial^\alpha \partial_\alpha (\delta q) d^3x \quad (26)$$

where the operator $\partial^\alpha \partial_\alpha$ represents the D'Alembertian (wave operator) in (2+1)-dimensional space-time.

By using Stokes' theorem, eq.(25) can be written as

$$\delta h_{\text{go}} = -\frac{1}{2\pi} \sum_{k=1}^N W_k \int_{V_k} \partial^\alpha \partial_\alpha (\delta q) d^3x = 0 \quad (27)$$

By the variational principle, the integral (27) must hold for all possible variations δq , implying

$$\sum_{k=1}^N W_k \partial^\alpha \partial_\alpha q = 0 \quad (28)$$

Eq.(28) is the field equations we look for. The weak geometric optical knot is the special solution of the field equations (28) i.e. the special form of the phase in which its phase gradient has a non-trivial holonomy, anholonomy. Anholonomy here is after parallel transporting, the phase gradient along a closed curve (a loop) in a given space-time and then bringing it back to its starting point, the phase gradient has rotated or changed due to the curvature of the space-time.

Analogous to hydrodynamics, eq.(28) is identical to the curl-free velocity³²

$$\Omega = \varepsilon^{ij} \partial_i v_j = 0 \quad (29)$$

where Ω denotes the vorticity and v_j is the velocity. The consequence of the curl-free vector field is the vector field can be written as the gradient of a scalar function³³, since the curl of a gradient is always zero, as written below

$$v_j = \partial_j s \quad (30)$$

where s is a scalar function.

Since the phase q is a scalar, the vector field, namely, the phase gradient field $\partial_j q$ created from it, normally satisfies $\varepsilon^{ij} \partial_i \partial_j q = 0$. This is true in the absence of any sources that can generate gradient field lines (vector field), but when there is a singularity in the region within the closed path, the curl is not zero³⁴. The condition (29) means that the velocity, v_j , has no local rotation i.e. it describes an irrotational flow. The velocity is identical to the phase gradient. It means that the phase does not support the local rotational effects. So, how can we obtain knotted structures when the system is curl-free? A possible answer is even if the local vorticity (or curl) is zero, the global structure of the scalar field may still encode a knotted topology through its phase function.

In physics, the solutions of wave equations in two and three dimensional space often possess phase singularities. At the point of phase singularity, the phase of the wave is undefined and wave intensity vanishes. Phase singularities are generically points in two dimensional space and form a network of lines in three dimensional space. Around the phase singularity points in two dimensions or phase singularity lines in three dimensions, the phase changes by 2π times an integer. This integer is the so-called topological charge (the strength of the singularity) of the phase singularity objects (points or lines). In three dimensional space, a important case is that the phase singularity lines are closed and knotted curves, these knot-like configurations exist in a variety of physical scenarios,

including Bose-Einstein condensations, chemical reaction and molecular diffusion systems, optical wave systems and field theory³⁵.

Let us consider the scalar phase function as solutions of eq.(28) given by

$$q(x, y, t) = m \cdot \arg(z) + \alpha t \quad (31)$$

where $z = x + iy$ is the complex representation of the two-dimensional position vector \vec{r} with x and y denoting the Cartesian components and $\arg(z)$ denotes the angular coordinate (or phase angle) with respect to the positive x -axis, measured from the origin.

In eq.(31), the constant m serves as a topological winding number that characterises the global behaviour of the phase around the origin. It reflects how many times the phase increases by 2π as one traverses a closed loop encircling the singularity at $z = 0$. This quantised winding encapsulates a topological charge, indicating that the phase field, although locally irrotational, possesses a non-trivial global structure. The constant α , on the other hand, represents the temporal rate of change of the phase. It introduces a linear dependence on time, effectively acting as a temporal frequency that governs the evolution of the phase field without altering its spatial topology. Together, m and α define a phase configuration that exhibits both global topological structure and temporal evolution. The parameter m controls the spatial winding of the phase around the origin, encoding a non-trivial topological charge, while α governs the uniform temporal growth of the phase, introducing dynamical behaviour without affecting its spatial topology.

The presence of a topological singularity is a necessary condition for the emergence of global phase variation. A topological singularity refers to a point or region at which the phase function q becomes undefined or non-smooth, not due to a local discontinuity, but as a consequence of the global structure imposed by the topology of the field. To illustrate this, let us consider for a simplicity the time-independent form of eq.(31) as written below

$$q(x, y) = m \cdot \arg z \quad (32)$$

At the origin (0,0), the function $\arg z$ is undefined due to the multivalued nature of the complex argument: approaching the origin from different directions yields different values of the angle. Consequently, the phase function $q(x, y)$ can not be extended continuously and smoothly to the entire plane including the origin, and thus the point (0,0) constitutes a topological singularity.

The significance of this singularity becomes evident when considering the behaviour of the phase along a closed loop. A nontrivial global phase shift occurs only if the loop encircles the singularity. If the loop does not enclose the origin, the argument function remains single-valued and smooth along the path, leading to zero net phase change

$$\oint_{\gamma} \nabla q \cdot d\vec{l} = 0 \quad (33)$$

However, if the loop encloses the singularity at the origin, the phase accumulates a net change of $2\pi m$, due to the winding of the argument function

$$\oint_{\gamma} \nabla q \cdot d\vec{l} = \Delta q = 2\pi m \quad (34)$$

This behaviour is a manifestation of anholonomy, wherein the phase fails to return to its initial value after parallel transport along a closed curve, indicating the presence of a non-trivial topological structure that can not be continuously deformed away.

The topological nature of the phase singularity in eq.(31) ensures robustness under smooth deformations. Since the winding number m is an integer-valued topological invariant, it remains unchanged under small perturbations, thereby providing topological stability to the configuration. Dynamical stability can be examined by linearising the field equation (28) around this solution and analysing the evolution of perturbations. If the perturbations remain bounded over time, the solution can be regarded as dynamically stable. Further insight may be gained through numerical simulations or energy-based arguments, depending on the physical context.

X. DISCUSSION AND CONCLUSION

It has been realized that the role of topology has become more and more important in recent days and the future of physics. But to understand topology is complicated enough because topology is inherently related to nonlinearity. It has been widely believed that topological objects can not exist in linear theories, such as an Abelian Chern-Simons theory. But this belief can no longer be maintained. The discovery of the electromagnetic knot in vacuum Maxwell's theory more than thirty years ago has shown that the topological object could exist in the linear theory.

We adopt the idea¹⁻³ of the electromagnetic knot and apply it to geometrical optics. This is because electromagnetism and geometrical optics, basically are the same theory for describing light whereas geometrical optics (eikonal equation) can be derived from Maxwell's theory.

The scalar potentials, such as the scalar fields, could be described using wave language. Both could be denoted by the amplitude times the exponential of iq , where q is the phase, and i is the imaginary number. The related (real) vector potential can be written using the Clebsch (scalar) variables, f , and q (11).

The Clebsch variables are not uniquely defined, but many different choices are possible for them. In this way, the vector potential can be understood simply. These Clebsch variables are related to any divergenceless vector field, i.e. the divergence of any vector field gives the zero result. Examples of a divergenceless vector field are the vorticity in hydrodynamics, i.e. $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{W} = 0$, so $\vec{W} = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{v}$ where \vec{v} is the velocity field vector, and in electromagnetism $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{B} = 0$, $\vec{B} = \vec{\nabla} \times \vec{A}$ where \vec{B} is the magnetic

field, \vec{A} is the potential. The condition $\vec{\nabla} \cdot \vec{W} = 0$ implies that vorticity is solenoidal, meaning it is sourceless or has no sinks. The vorticity originates from the curl of the velocity field. This means that the "source" of vorticity is the rotational motion of the velocity field rather than a scalar charge such as in electromagnetism. We can observe the non-zero vorticity phenomenon in the rotational flows of fluids, e.g. a whirlpool.

Expressing the gauge potential and the related field strength tensor in terms of the Clebsch variables simplifies the formulation. The Clebsch variables, by showing explicitly the amplitude function and the phase, enable the separation of the underlying physical dynamics (the amplitude function, the phase) and certain properties of the gauge potential and the field strength tensor, such as topological structures. Separating the gauge potential and the field strength tensor into their amplitude function and phase makes the topological features inherent in the gauge potential and the field strength tensor more apparent.

The problems in the higher dimension can often be more complex than those in the lower dimension. By mapping onto the lower dimensional space, such as in the non-trivial Hopf maps, the problem becomes simpler, without losing the information about the non-trivial topological properties of space. If we relate the non-trivial Hopf maps to physics, we could interpret the Hopf maps to represent the properties of a set of subset fields, consisting of the complex scalar fields.

We see from eq. (19), the Levi-Civita symbol has a very important role related to the topology. The most significant role of the Levi-Civita symbol is it introduces an antisymmetric structure. This antisymmetric structure is the key to defining the topological properties of the gauge potential and the related field strength tensor. By introducing the Levi-Civita symbol, the gauge potential is coupled to the field strength to ensure the gauge potential has a well-defined curl (i.e. a non-trivial field strength) in the system. This non-trivial field strength can be interpreted as a flux through the loop. A flux here could be understood as a measure of how much field lines of the field strength passes through a surface. The flux through the loop refers to the flux of the field strength through the surface enclosed by the boundary of the surface, the loop.

We consider Minkowski space-time to represent a vacuum; both are identical. We argue that light propagates in a vacuum with constant velocity, so it is reasonable to treat a vacuum as flat space-time.

We have shown that a weak geometric optical knot can arise as a topological structure in an Abelian Chern-Simons theory in (2+1)-dimensional vacuum space-time. The field equation leads to a phase field whose gradient is locally irrotational, but globally non-trivial when the phase contains singularities. This results in a quantized circulation around closed loops, characterised by non-trivial holonomy.

Using a time-dependent phase ansatz, we obtain a class

of solutions with topological charge. These knots are stable under small deformations and reflect the underlying Hopf structure in the field. The result highlights a new link between topology and gauge-theoretic dynamics in geometrical optics.

Theoretically, the empirical or the observational evidence to support the existence of the weak geometric optical knot in vacuum (2+1)-dimensional space-time is guaranteed by the formal equivalence between the electromagnetic knot and the weak geometric optical knot formulations for which the electromagnetic knot solutions had been known to exist^{1-3,36}.

Does the geometric optical knot exist in the universe or a laboratory? Ball lightning³⁷ probably is an electromagnetic (so the geometric optical) knot in the universe³⁸ where tokamaks and devices constructed to produce fireballs are two possible laboratory settings to observe ball lightning³⁸. A (geometric optical) knot of light may be generated using tightly focused circularly polarized laser beams³⁹.

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